

On Testing Facebook: One of Social Network

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Abstract:

Among various websites, social networks, and platforms on internet, privacy related policies does plays an important role. Here in this paper, we have attempted to test, the privacy policies and user information; as user information are more talk as topics of privacy, with an example of Facebook. Logos, Trademarks of Facebooks are copyright of Facebook itself, and we shall discuss based on author's user profile in facebook.

Introduction:

We shall begin with author's.own facebook profile, with username in facebook as arjundahal001. Here basic, public details, allowed by facebook, to share, are provided, which includes beginning from privacy policies like; allowing public to read, allowing only friends, allowing friends of friends, or not allowing anyone, and keeping privacy policy to self.

Two more pictures are provided, which shows downloading facebook data as zip file, as provided by facebook, and another one, shows, that archive requested by Facebook, is valid only for 4 days, and does expires, and is provided in html format.

Test:

What would Facebook do, when I would store the data, downloaded from Facebook into, some another sites like as Zenodo, or even any Journal or repository.

Thus, we shall deposit the data downloaded partially and is not completely, as due to larger file size, error occured while downloading, earlier time.

Furthermore Test:

Since my facebook profile is verified, and question lies using facebook, as per various identifiers like as OID, DOI, as well as other identifiers in internet, so that, some complete description would be available, along with abstraction and indexing topics about any user, in internet. It is true that, by adding links, we can link topics, but our question lies, in auto update, and that would violate privacy policies for me, not of Facebook (I guess), because, source codes or such codes of programming, too might have been studied, before making it, available for any user to download.

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complete copy, or you can select only the types of information and date ranges you want. You can choose to receive your information in an HTML format that is easy to view, or a JSON format, which could allow another service to more easily import it.

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Arjun Dahal

Arjun Dahal

Passionate in Physics, Mathematics, Music, Literature, and Philosophy.

[Edit Profile](#)

- Worked at Student
- Studied Theoretical physics at **Tri-Chandra College**
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Birthday **February 11, 1996**

Gender **Male**

Languages **Nepalian and English language**

Actknowledgements:

My actknowledgement goes to fellows, or even machines, bots, bugs, or such topics, due to which, sometimes I do face problem in facebook, like as message box appearing like as cursor, blinking time

and again, when I want to do text message, and another problem is, when I do log out, Facebook does asks, if it(my) account is my account or wrong account, and that would be a bad troll, where as keeping archival of data, would allow us to test along with expiry of data, and autoupdate, depending upon user profile, because, it is timeline, that is allowed to be publicly seen, even by me.

Further Actnowledgements:

I had inquired to Facebook Help Center, about those topics, and am waiting for their response, where as we shall continue the test.